

A Design Tool for Laminated Composites

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Summary

New computer aided design tools are needed to effectively exploit today's new advanced continuous fiber composite materials. The manufacturing process, mechanical properties and cost of laminated composite parts are tightly coupled, and must be evaluated simultaneously to The authors have investigated the deformation modes of woven composite materials when conforming to complex curvature parts and have validated a computer simulation technology which can accurately predict fiber deformation. The results of the simulation can be used to support a concurrent engineering methodology which would include complete material property synthesis providing a foundation for efficient and precise structural analysis of laminated composites, automatic generation of 2D flat ply profiles, early warning of manufacturing complications, calculation of exact laminate thickness and accurate mold spacing for mold machining.

1 Introduction

Today's advanced continuous fiber composite materials offer dramatic performance capabilities, opening many new and exciting engineering possibilities. However, the promise of tremendous increases in strength and stiffness, together with considerable weight savings has a price. Engineering with continuous fiber composites places new demands on the designer and analyst, often greatly increasing

development costs. Due to uncertainty in the mechanical properties additional material is added to provide an adequate factor of safety. This over design wipes out much of the potential weight savings and adds significantly to the cost of the part.

The cost and performance of composite parts are tightly coupled to part design, and material and manufacturing decisions. The part geometry constrains the manufacturing process which in turn constrains the possible fiber orientations upon which the mechanical properties depend. To take full advantage of these impressive materials, designers and analysts require a new tool that integrates part geometry, material, mechanical property synthesis and manufacturing. This paper describes the functionality of that tool. It is the key that engineers need to unlock the incredible potential of advanced composites quickly and at reasonable cost.

2 Composite Design Tool

Despite the continued development of computer aided tools in the general engineering domain, there are still few such tools for composite part design. The design process that is used by many engineering organizations for composite parts is expensive, tedious, inaccurate and often plagued with long sequential sub-processes and multiple iterations before a design can be completed. A typical design begins with an engineer specifying key part parameters such as part geometry, structural properties,

materials, and the fiber orientation of each layer in the laminate. Then an analyst makes an approximation of the part and mechanical properties and performs the required analysis. If problems are found, the engineer is notified. Finally the part design is passed off to manufacturing for generation of flat patterns, tools, and process design. This step is often months after the initial part design and any changes to make manufacturing easier or even possible are difficult and very expensive.

Figure 1. Current part design process

Many of the steps described in the current process are manual and involve a trial and error approach. For example, when generating flat patterns for complex curvature parts designers estimate a 2D profile for the 3D ply definition by calculating curve lengths on the surface. Then an oversize piece of material is cut and placed in the mold, manually trimmed to the 3D ply boundary. The resulting ply is then removed from the mold, flattened and its perimeter digitized for future use. For a typical aerospace part involving

one hundred or more plies this process can take many man weeks. Clearly better computer aided tools are needed to automate and improve these manual processes. At the same time such a tool could bring manufacturability and cost feedback to the engineer while he is making those initial and crucial design decisions. Research on such a tool has been done at Draper over the last 3 years.

To support our work in the development of efficient manufacturing processes for woven composite materials Draper began an investigation into woven fabric deformation. As part of this research we developed a drape simulation code based on work done at the University of Delaware's Center for Composite Materials [1].

Tests were done to compare the fiber orientations predicted by the computer simulation with actual parts formed on a double diaphragm former [2]. A grid of small dots was silk-screened onto the material to be formed. The LCMS or Laser Coordinate Measurement System developed at CSDL was used to digitize the grid points on the formed parts and capture the three dimensional coordinates of the tows. The fiber orientation could then be compared with those predicted by the simulation. When shape conformance was good (no wrinkles etc.) there was very good correlation between the actual data and the simulation.

The current simulation will predict fiber orientations for complex curvature surfaces. Deformation angles and lamina thicknesses are also calculated. The fiber orientations can be plotted as seen in figure 2. Contour plots of deformation angle and lamina thicknesses can also be generated.

Figure 2. Simulation results for a hemisphere

3 Precise and Efficient Analysis

Within the general engineering domain, there is a wealth of new computer aided tools for design and analysis available on the engineer's desktop. These computer simulations can predict how structures or processes will behave under specific loading conditions. Application of these powerful software tools to laminated composites has been severely limited by the difficulty in modeling the mechanical properties of a part. To make structural analysis of laminated composites cost effective, engineers are forced to make many simplifying assumptions such as, uniform mechanical properties and constant laminate thickness. These assumptions are rarely accurate and as a result the analyses are rough estimates at best and can lead to serious structural errors or wasteful over design.

A woven composite design tool could automate the calculation of accurate and complete laminate material properties and thicknesses for even the most complex composite parts, thus providing means for efficient and precise structural analysis of laminated composites. The tool would calculate the fiber orientations and the resulting laminate thicknesses by simulating the conformance of each ply to the product surface. The plies may be of arbitrary

shapes and different materials. The simulation automatically accounts for the surface offset and thickness build up of lower plies. All the ply data is combined to synthesize precise laminate material properties and thickness for inclusion in finite element analysis.

Material Property Synthesis

The anisotropic nature of continuous fiber composite materials makes precise specification of material properties critical to the analysis of composites. The mechanical properties of a composite laminate, such as strength and stiffness, are dependent on the local fiber directions that can vary significantly from point to point in the final part. Some other important material properties, such as thermal expansion, and thermal conductivity are also a function of fiber direction. The accurate prediction of the fiber orientations, the primary determinant of material properties, is extremely difficult and tedious to do by hand in simple parts and impossible in most real cases.

For example, woven composite fabrics undergo extensive shear deformation when conforming to surfaces having compound curvature. This deformation, coupled with the propagation of lay-up boundary conditions and weave kinematics, makes the prediction of fiber orientations for each of the many plies of a typical laminate non-trivial. The material properties for each element in the analysis model are calculated using composite laminate theory and the computed fiber orientations of each ply near the element centroid. The large number of plies of differing geometries and orientations common in composite parts further compound these difficulties. Currently no tool is available to assist engineers in defining individual plies and calculating the resulting material properties and

laminate thicknesses for arbitrary geometries.

A simple hemisphere draped with two woven plies demonstrates the dramatic effect part geometry can have on composite material properties. A laminate with one ply with fibers running $0^\circ/90^\circ$ at the top of the hemisphere and another oriented $\pm 45^\circ$ would exhibit approximately isotropic material properties in the plane of the laminate. However, after the plies conform to the surface of the hemisphere, the fiber orientations near the equator have changed dramatically. At the point highlighted in the figure there is only one fiber within 70° of the equator to resist hoop stresses. Therefore assumptions of isotropic or uniform material properties are obviously inappropriate.

Figure 3. Effect of fabric deformation on fiber orientation.

Calculation of Exact Laminate Thickness

Lay-up not only affects fiber orientation, local lamina thickness can vary significantly. On the hemisphere, the thickness of each of the plies increased by 50% at some points on the surface. The combined thickness of the two plies

increased by over 20% in some locations. Variations in thickness of this magnitude are common and greatly effect stress, buckling, and inter-lamina shear analyses. Variations in fiber orientations and laminate thickness similar to those shown on the hemisphere occur in all complex curvature parts. Even simple planar parts often contain many plies of various patterns and orientations that combine to make material property definition difficult, tedious and error prone.

4 Manufacturing Applications

Generation of 2D Flat Ply Patterns

The woven composites design tool could determine the 2D flat profile for a ply such that after lay-up, the ply will conform exactly to a 3D ply boundary defined on part surface. The tool would produce precise ply profiles in minutes, compared with the days now required to manually generate flat patterns. These precise ply profiles could be passed on to a ply nesting package and then used to drive an NC ply cutter.

Figure 4. Automatic generation of 2D flat patterns from 3D ply definitions.

Supports Concurrent Engineering

A composite design tool would provide critical support to concurrent engineering efforts, by bringing manufacturing feedback into the design process. The tool also has capabilities which ease and speed the manufacture

of laminated composite parts while eliminating costly late changes, errors and rework.

Identification of Manufacturing Complications

Such a tool would not only improve the productivity of designing composite products, it would improve the quality of the manufactured parts. By identifying potential manufacturing problems during design, the tool helps avoid costly changes later in the design process. The tool can identify and alert the user to manufacturing problems such as wrinkling (exceeding lock angle of the material), tow spreading, and bridging of the composite plies.

Such a composite design tool would also reduce unit costs, by allowing engineers to optimize their designs, eliminating cost and weight from over design. A CAD tool for composites would lower manufacturing costs by identifying potential manufacturing problems during design when correction is easy. Finding and correcting such problems on the factory floor is much more expensive and results costly delays. The tool also reduces tool costs by precisely calculating the overall thickness of the plies for the entire part and generating the offset surfaces for machining the tool.

Accurate Matched Mold Spacing

The laminate thickness data generated during a simulation can be used to precisely control the mold gap and determine surface offsets for machining matched molds. This guarantees accurate fiber volumes in the final part, and avoids common manufacturing complications such as dry spots and resin rich areas, both consequences of laminate thickness estimation errors.

5 CONCLUSION

A computer aided design tool for woven composite materials would dramatically improve productivity of design, analysis and manufacture of composite parts made from woven materials. This tool would also improve the quality of the parts, eliminate wasteful over design and result in lower cost parts. Based on our research and experience such a tool is feasible would complement many of the generic engineering tools that currently exist.

Figure 5. Future part design process

REFERENCES

1. Van West, Barry P., "A Simulation of the Draping and a Model of the Consolidation of Commingled Fabrics". Center for Composite Materials Technical Report (CCM Report 90-07), Composites Manufacturing Science Laboratory, University of Delaware.
2. S. Luby and E. Bernardon, "Design of Fabric Preforms for Double Diaphragm Forming", 9th DoD/NASA/FAA Conference on Fibrous Composites in Structural Design.